

COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX FERRIC FERROCYANIDE (PRUSSIAN BLUE) BY POTENTIOMETRIC METHOD

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The composition of ferric ferrocyanide has been studied by potentiometric method using ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode. The composition arrived at closely approximates to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, but is influenced by factors such as hydrolysis and adsorption.

According to the equation

the oxidation potential of the ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode is given by

$$E = E_0 + 0.059 \ln \frac{[Fe(CN)_6]^{III}}{[Fe(CN)_6]^{IV}} \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

In the titration of ferric chloride with potassium ferrocyanide solution containing a little ferricyanide (Galetti, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1864, ii, 2, 83; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1865, 4, 213) so long as there is an excess of ferric ions in the solution, the concentration of ferrocyanide is small and so the potential of the electrode is high. As soon as the ferric ions are quantitatively precipitated, the next drop of ferrocyanide solution causes an increase in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{III}$, and hence a decrease in the oxidation potential occurs. The equivalence point may therefore be detected.

EXPERIMENTAL

'Analar' (B. D. H.) reagents were used, and standard solutions of potassium ferrocyanide and ferric chloride were prepared. In all the titrations potassium ferrocyanide containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used (Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations"). Electrode used was of platinised platinum foil (Muller, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 44), and it was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. Curves were plotted between the volume of ferrocyanide added and the E (observed), and from the fall of the curves the equivalence point could be found out.

TABLE I
 $M/20\text{-}FeCl_2$ solution. = 20 c.c. (Fig. 1).

$M/5\text{-}K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/5\text{-}K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/5\text{-}K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.	E (obs.).
0.0 c.c.	0.4500 volt	2.8 c.c.	0.3555 volt	4.6 c.c.	0.2540 volt
0.5	0.4250	3.0	0.3500	5.0	0.2350
1.0	0.4060	3.2	0.3440	5.2	0.2290
1.5	0.3895	3.4	0.3400	5.4	0.2200
1.8	0.3810	3.5	0.3380	5.6	0.2150
2.0	0.3760	3.6	0.3320	5.8	0.2090
2.2	0.3715	3.8	0.3295	6.0	0.2050
2.4	0.3660	4.0	0.3195	6.5	0.2000
2.6	0.3610	4.2	0.2960	7.0	0.1900
		4.4	0.2750		

TABLE II

 $M/40\text{-FeCl}_2$ solution = 20 c.c. (Fig. 2).

$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).
0.0 c.c.	0.3900 volt	3.6 c.c.	0.3200 volt	5.4 c.c.	0.2150 volt
0.5	0.3775	3.8	0.3105	5.6	0.2085
1.0	0.3700	4.0	0.3000	6.0	0.2000
1.5	0.3620	4.2	0.2900	6.5	0.1900
2.0	0.3520	4.4	0.2700	7.0	0.1850
2.5	0.3475	4.6	0.2500	7.5	0.1800
3.0	0.3350	4.8	0.2355	8.0	0.1750
3.0	0.3300	5.0	0.2250	8.5	0.1725
3.4	0.3255	5.2	0.2200		

TABLE III

 $M/20\text{-FeCl}_2$ solution = 20 c. c. (Fig. 3).

$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).
0.0 c.c.	0.4650 volt	6.0 c.c.	0.3500 volt	9.4 c.c.	0.2500 volt
0.5	0.4480	6.5	0.3425	9.4	0.2800
1.0	0.4230	6.8	0.3400	9.6	0.2700
1.5	0.4100	7.0	0.3375	9.8	0.2550
2.0	0.4000	7.4	0.3320	10.0	0.2520
2.5	0.3905	7.8	0.3275	10.2	0.2450
3.0	0.3830	8.0	0.3250	10.4	0.2400
3.5	0.3775	8.4	0.3175	11.0	0.2250
4.0	0.3720	8.6	0.3100	12.0	0.2155
5.0	0.3590	8.8	0.3050	13.0	0.2075
5.5	0.3540	9.0	0.3000	14.0	0.2055

TABLE IV

 $M/20\text{-FeCl}_2$ solution = 20 c.c. (Fig. 4).

$M/20\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/20\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).	$M/20\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ added.	E (obs.).
0.0 c.c.	0.4450 volt	12.0 c.c.	0.3480 volt	18.8 c.c.	0.3080 volt
1.0	0.4325	13.0	0.3430	19.0	0.3030
2.0	0.4190	14.0	0.3400	19.2	0.2980
3.0	0.4065	14.4	0.3370	19.4	0.2950
4.0	0.3980	15.0	0.3340	19.6	0.2900
5.0	0.3890	15.4	0.3320	19.8	0.2880
6.0	0.3825	15.8	0.3305	20.0	0.2860
7.0	0.3760	16.4	0.3280	20.4	0.2820
8.0	0.3695	17.0	0.3240	20.8	0.2780
9.0	0.3630	17.6	0.3200	21.4	0.2740
10.0	0.3560	18.0	0.3170	22.0	0.2710
11.0	0.3510	18.4	0.3130	23.0	0.2670
11.5	0.3495	18.6	0.3110	24.0	0.2640

TABLE V

Summary of results of potentiometric titrations.

Titre values for 20 c.c. of FeCl_3
Calc. for the formation of comps.

Fig.	$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	FeCl_3 .	Observed from curves.	$\text{KFe}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$.	$\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$
1.	M/5	M/20	4.7 c.c.	5 c.c.	3.75 c.c.
2.	M/10	M/40	4.8	5	3.75
3.	M/10	M/20	9.7	10	7.50
4.	M/20	M/20	19.6	20	15.0

DISCUSSION

From Table V it is clear that the observed titre values, which correspond to the sudden fall in potential in the curves are slightly lower than the theoretical ones required for the formation of the compound $\text{KFe}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$, while they are widely different from those required for the formation of the compound $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$. Kolthoff and Fur-

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

mann (*loc. cit.*) and Muller and Takagami (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1928, 73, 284) also observed

that in precipitation reactions the maximum leap did not occur at the theoretical point of equivalence.

Fig. 4

In conductivity titrations also we have observed that the formation of $K_4Fe[Fe(CN)_6]$ is supported when potassium ferrocyanide is added to ferric chloride (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 141). The slight discrepancy between the theoretical and the observed titre values can be explained by the tendency of the complex formed to hydrolyse. Due to hydrolysis, the potassium ferrocyanide released, will react with some ferric chloride solution with the result that the observed titre values would be lower than the required theoretical values.

The phenomenon of adsorption has also been observed in the formation of this complex and this too,

would tend to lower the titre values. Hydrolysis and adsorption phenomena disturbing the equilibrium

seem to be responsible for these discrepancies between the calculated and the observed values.

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. S.S. Deshpande for the interest he took in these investigations.